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A REVIEW ON NASAL DRUG DELIVERY: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

For local and systemic delivery of many therapeutic drugs, intranasal administration is a viable alternative. In comparison to other mucosae, the nasal mucosa is easy to reach. Intranasal medication administration is painless and non-invasive, making it ideal for youngsters. In an emergency situation, patients or doctors can easily perform the application. The therapeutic effects of intranasal medication administration are felt quickly (local or systemic). The medication is not degraded in the gastrointestinal tract and does not undergo first-pass hepatic metabolism when administered through nasal spray. The trinity of drug, transportation, and application device is indestructible. As a result, its selection is critical to the development of successful nasal products. Intranasal administration is discussed in this paper's practicality and potential. The purpose of this review is to provide some information about nasal drug delivery systems, including limitations, benefits, mechanisms of drug absorption, anatomy of the nasal cavity, factors affecting nasal drug delivery, strategies to improve nasal absorption, strategies to extend the duration of drug formulations within the nasal cavity, leading to improved nasal drug absorption, novel drug formulations, and types of nasal drug delivery systems with uses of nasal drug delivery in various diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

NASAL DRUG DELIVERY

Nasal drug delivery has raised a great deal of interest as a convenient and dependable method for systemic medication administration. Nasal sprays are used to deliver therapeutic substances either locally or systemically within the nasal cavities. It's especially useful for compounds that are useless when taken orally but are most strong when injected. This is due to high vascularity, a large floor area, the avoidance of hepatic first metabolism via gut wall metabolism, and/or gastrointestinal tract damage. Because the nasal mucosa has so many benefits for target transport, a wide range of healing compounds can be delivered intranasally for topical, systemic, and relevant anxious device movements. [1]

For instance, localized nasal drug transport is generally used to deal with situation associated with the nasal hollow space, which include congestion, rhinitis, sinusitis and associated allergic situations. In latest years, attaining a systemic drug motion the usage of the nostril because the accesses portal into the frame has obtained extra interest. Now a day's a couple of kinds of components are used to manage drug via way of nasal course, which incorporates nasal sprays, nasal drops, nasal powder, nasal gels and nasal insert, etc. The administration of medication through the nostrils within the spray dosage form is a non-invasive method that provides a rapid onset of therapeutic action. Patient compliance has been greatly influenced by the nasal spray dosage shape since it is cost-effective, easy to use/deliver, and self-administrable. As a result, nasal drug delivery has become a popular method of drug administration with a promising future. [2]

ADVANTAGES

- 1) There is no drug degradation observed in the gastrointestinal tract.
- 2) First-pass metabolism of the liver is avoided
- 3) Rapid drug absorption and onset of action can be achieved.
- 4) The nasal bioavailability of smaller drug molecules is good.
- 5) Drugs that are not orally absorbed can be delivered to the systemic circulation by nasal drug delivery.
- 6) Convenient for the patients, in particular for those on long time therapy, while as compared with parenteral medication. [3,4]

DISADVANTAGES

- 1) The amount of drug delivery to the nasal cavity is limited to 25-200 μL .
- 2) High molecular weight (mass limit 1 kDa) drugs cannot be delivered by the third route.
- 3) This route is affected by morbidity.
- 4) Drug permeability is affected by normal defense mechanisms such as mucous cilia clearance and ciliary body attacks.
- 5) Absorption area is smaller than GIT.
- 6) It faces an enzymatic barrier to drug permeability. [5]

ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF NASAL CAVITY

The nasal cavity is divided into two by the nasal septum and extends behind the nasopharynx. On the other hand, the foremost part of the nasal cavity, the nasal vestibular, opens toward the face through the nostrils. The nasal cavity consists of three main areas: the nasal vestibule, the sense of smell, and the respiratory area. By folding the side wall of the nasal cavity, the surface area of the nose can be increased by about 150 cm^2 , which is much larger than the smaller volume. This folded structure consists of three turbinates, top, middle and bottom. [6]

The main nasal airways with narrow passages are usually 13 mm wide, and these narrow structures help the nose perform its main function. The nasal cavity is covered with mucous membranes, which can be divided into two areas. This non-olfactory and olfactory epithelium contains a nasal vestibule covered with multi-layered squamous epithelial cells such as skin, whereas the respiratory area is typically covered by a large number of microvilli of the airway epithelium. Because it is broken, it has a large surface area. It can be used for drug absorption and circulation [7].

In this way, a layer of mucus is propelled from the front to the back of the nasal cavity. Goblet cells are located in the mucous membranes that line the turbinates and atria. It secretes mucus as mucous granules that swell in the nasal fluid to contribute to the mucous layer. Mucus secretions are composed of approximately 95% water, 2% mucin, 1% salt, 1% albumin, immunoglobulins, lysozyme, other proteins such as lactoferrin, and b 1% lipids. [8]. Mucus secretions provide immune protection against inhaled bacteria and viruses. It Covers the mucous membrane and protects it physically and enzymatically.

- (1) Slime has the ability to retain water.
- (2) Shows the electrical activity of the surface.
- (3) Enables efficient heat transfer.
- (5) Acts as an adhesive and transports particulate matter towards the nasopharynx. [9]

Nose Diagram

Nose: The nose is a complex multifunctional organ. The nose is the front door to the airways.

External nose:

The external nose is a pyramidal structure in the center of the face, based on the skeleton of the face, with the tip protruding forward. During exercise, such as when nasal breathing is increased, increased diastolic muscle activity helps increase patency of the nasal airways.

Vestibule:

The first part of the airway that comes into contact with the external environment is the vestibule. Unlike the rest of the nasal cavity, the vestibule is lined with stratified squamous epithelium. The vestibule also contains heat receptors not found in the respiratory epithelial-lined part of the nasal cavity.

Nasal flap and airflow:

The nasal flap is just behind the nasal vestibule. It is surrounded outward by the caudal end of the superior lateral cartilage, medially by the septum, and inferior by the lower edge of the piriform aperture.

Septum:

The septum divides the nasal cavity into two separate compartments, increasing the total surface area of the mucous membrane. It consists of the anterior cartilage that supports the tip of the nose and the posterior bone that is formed by the vertical plates of the ethmoid and vomer.

Concha:

The turbinate is the three, rarely four, tendril-shaped protrusions of the turbinate. The lower two, called the inferior turbinate and the middle turbinate, are the most functionally important.

Nasopharyngeal area:

This is also called the "upper respiratory tract" and includes the airways from the nose to the larynx.

Smell area:

The olfactory area is located on the roof of the nasal cavity and extends slightly down the septum and sidewalls. Its neuroepithelium is the only part of the central nervous system that is directly exposed to the external environment. Like the respiratory epithelium, the olfactory epithelium is a pseudostratified epithelium, but it contains special olfactory receptor cells that are important for the sense of smell.

Nasal Secretions

Nasal secretions originate in general from submucosal glands and goblet cells. Mucus consists of water (95%); glycoproteins (2%); albumin, immunoglobulins, lysozyme, lactoferrin and different proteins (1%); inorganic salts (1%); and lipids (<1%). Glycoproteins are in low proportion, which offers mucus with its function viscoelastic properties. The mucus layer is split into the low viscosity decrease layer of approximately five–10 μm thick and the extra viscous higher layer of approximately 0.5–5 μm thick. The human nasal pH is about five–8.[10]

Profile of an ideal drug candidate for nasal drug delivery

Molecular weight < 500Da, log P<5.

Aqueous solubility < 50 mg/ml.

Dose potency < 5mg/dose/spray of puff per nostril.

Drug in solution: Ph approximately 5.5, osmolarity < 500 mosm/kg.

No nasal irritation from drug.

Volume 25-125 μ L per Nostril.

Nasal secretions	Epithelial characteristics cells/functions	vascularization	Permeability
Vestibule	Stratified squamous and keratinized	Low	Poor
Atrium	Stratified squamous cells/support	Low	Reduced
Olfactory region	Pseudostratified cells/support Sustentacular cells /support and synthetic - olfactory receptor cells/olfactory perception. -Basal cells/progenitors of other cell types.	High	Direct access to CNS

MECHANISM OF NASAL ABSORPTION

Drugs absorbed through the nasal passages must pass through the mucus layer. It is the first step in absorption. Small unmodified drugs easily pass through this layer, while large charged drugs are difficult to pass. The main protein in mucus is mucin, which tends to bind to solutes and prevent diffusion. Also, structural changes in the mucous layer can occur as a result of environmental changes (ie, pH, temperature, etc.). A large number of absorption mechanisms have been previously established, but only two are mainly used: [11]

First mechanism This is an aqueous transport pathway, also known as the paracellular pathway, but it is slow and passive. The intranasal absorption of water-soluble substances has an inverse log-log relationship with their molecular weight. Low bioavailability is indicated by drugs with molecular weights above 1000 daltons.

Second mechanism Including transport via the lipid pathway, also known as transcellular process. It is involved in the transport of lipophilic drugs that show a rate dependence on lipophilicity. The drug also crosses the cell membrane in active transport pathways via carrier-mediated means or transport through tight junction openings. [12]

BARRIERS TO NASAL ABSORPTION

Nasal drug delivery systems have a simple and easy formulation strategy and are considered to be a useful path. The therapeutic effect and toxicity of intranasally administered drugs are affected by many factors [13]. The following factors are barriers to drug absorption through the nasal passages:

- i) **Low bioavailability:** Lipophilic drugs are generally well absorbed through the nasal passages compared to polar drugs. The pharmacokinetic profile of lipophilic drugs is often the same as that obtained after intravenous injection, with bioavailability approaching 100%. Polar drugs with a molecular weight of less than 1000 Da usually cross the membrane by the latter route. [14]
- ii) **Insufficient membrane transport:** Another important factor in inadequate membrane transport is the general rapid clearance of pharmaceuticals administered from the nasal cavity by the MCC mechanism. This is especially true for drugs that are not easily absorbed through the nasal mucosa. [15]
- iii) **Enzymatic degradation:** Another cause of poor transport of peptides and proteins, especially through the nasal mucosa (although usually considered less important) is intranasal or intranasal molecules. Is the possibility of enzymatic degradation. It passes through the epithelial barrier. Both of these sites contain exopeptidases such as mono proteases and diamino peptidases that can cleave peptides at the N-terminus and C-terminus, and endopeptidases such as serine and cysteine that can attack internal peptide bonds. [16]

FACTORS INFLUENCING NASAL DRUG ABSORPTION

Several factors affect the systemic bioavailability of nasal medications. These factors can affect the physicochemical properties of the drug, the anatomical and physiological properties of the nasal cavity, and the type and properties of the selected nasal drug delivery system. Factors that affect the absorption of nasal drugs are:

A) Physiological factors

1. Blood supply and nerve regulation: The nasal mucosa is a highly permeable area. High blood supply by parasympathetic stimulation leads to sympathetic stimulation to relaxation, regulation of increase and decrease of stimulation to relaxation, and congestion and low blood supply by regulation of increase and decrease of permeating drug amount, respectively.

2. Nasal secretions: Nasal secretions are produced by the anterior serous and serous glands. The permeability of the drug through the nasal mucosa is affected by:

- **Runny nose viscosity:** If the sol layer is too thin, the viscous surface layer suppresses the beating of the cilia. If the sol layer is too thick, it loses contact with the cilia and impairs mucous fimbria clearance.
- **Drug solubility in nasal secretions:** Drug penetration requires solubilization. The drug must have physicochemical properties suitable for dissolving in the nasal discharge.
- **The pH of nasal:** pH fluctuations is 5.5 to 6.5 for adults and 5.0 to 7.0 for babies. If the pH of the nose is lower than the pKa of the drug, then the penetrating molecule is present as a non-ionized species under such conditions, resulting in greater drug penetration.

B) Physicochemical properties of drug:

1) Molecular weight and size: Drug penetration is determined by the molecular weight, molecular size, hydrophilicity and lipophilicity of the compound. For 1 kDa compounds, bioavailability can be predicted directly from MW's knowledge. In general, the bioavailability of these large molecules ranges from 0.5% to 5%.

2) Solubility: The main factor that determines drug absorption through biological membranes is the solubility of the drug. Lipophilic drugs have low solubility in aqueous secretions. Depending on the solubility, water-soluble drugs are absorbed by passive diffusion and lipophilic drugs are absorbed by active transport.

3) Lipophilicity: The penetration of compounds through the nasal mucosa usually increases with increasing lipophilicity. The nasal mucosa seems to be lipophilic in nature.

4) pKa and partition coefficient: According to pH partition theory, non-ionized species are better absorbed than ionized species, and the same fact applies to nasal absorption. There is a certain relationship between the pKa of these drugs and nasal absorption.

C) Physicochemical properties of formulation:

1) Physical form of the product: The liquid product is less effective than the powder form in delivering insulin to rabbits. In the more viscous formulation, less efficient systemic nasal drug delivery was observed. Viscous formulations help minimize nasal discharge.

2) pH: The degree of ionization of the drug is related to the pH of the pharmaceutical product because it is governed by the hypothesis of the pH distribution. Nasal formulations should be adjusted to the proper pH to avoid irritation, achieve efficient absorption and prevent the growth of pathogens. The pH of the ideal formulation should be adjusted between 4.5 and 6.5.

3) Osmotic pressure: Since the tonicity of the preparation generally greatly affects the nasal mucosa, the isotonic preparation is preferable [17, 18].

Nasal Allergies/Diseases

1. Allergic Rhinitis

Allergic rhinitis is inflammation of the inside of the nose caused by an allergen, such as pollen, dust, mould or flakes of skin from certain animals. Allergic rhinitis (AR) is an allergen induced inflammation of the membranes lining the nose. It affects between 10% and 30% of the general population and is one of the most common diseases in the United States.[19]

SYMPTOMS

AR is characterized by symptoms of runny nose, nasal itching, nasal congestion, and sneezing, but also may be associated with other symptoms such as postnasal drip, ocular itching or redness, ear fullness or itching, or headache.[20]

TREATMENT

Firstline therapies include oral or intranasal antihistamine agents or intranasal steroids. Treatments for allergic rhinitis include:

ANTI-HISTAMINES:

Medicines called antihistamines work well for treating allergy symptoms. They work by stopping your body from making histamine.

CORTICOSTEROIDS:

Nasal corticosteroid sprays are the most effective treatment for allergic rhinitis. Corticosteroid sprays are generally safe for children and adults. **DECONGESTANTS:** Decongestants may also be helpful for reducing symptoms such as nasal stuffiness. Do not use decongestant nasal drops for more than 3 days.

Other Medicines:

Leukotriene inhibitors are prescription drugs that block leukotrienes. These are chemicals released by the body in response to the allergens that cause symptoms. [21]

Type

There are two types of allergic rhinitis, seasonal and perennial. Seasonal allergies usually appear in the spring and autumn seasons and are usually a reaction to outdoor allergens such as pollen. Perennial allergies can occur year-round or at any time of the year in response to indoor substances such as mites and pet dander. [22]

COMPLICATIONS

Allergic rhinitis can cause complications in some cases. These include:

- ✓ Nasal polyps-an abnormal but non-cancerous (beneficial) fluid sac that grows in the nasal and sinuses
- ✓ Sinusitis-an infection caused by inflammation and swelling of the nose
- ✓ Prevents the drainage of mucus from the sinuses. [23]

2) NON - ALLERGIC RHINITIS Non allergic rhinitis is associated with chronic sneezing, stuffy nose, and runny nose for no apparent reason. Symptoms of non-allergic rhinitis are similar to those of hay fever (allergic rhinitis), but there are no usual signs of an allergic reaction. **Non-allergic** rhinitis can affect children and adults. But it is more common after the age of 20.

Symptoms

If you have non-allergic rhinitis, the symptoms may appear or disappear throughout the year. Signs and symptoms of non-allergic rhinitis include the following:

- Stuffy nose or runny nose
- Sneezing
- Sputum in the throat
- Cough

Treatment

There is no cure for non-allergic rhinitis. Many people manage their symptoms through self-care measures, environmental changes, and dosing. prescription medications can relieve nasal infections and relieve symptoms. These medicines include:

- ❖ Decongestant nasal drops to relieve stuffy nose.
- ❖ Antihistamine nasal drops that reduce inflammation in the nose.
- ❖ Corticosteroid nasal drops to relieve nasal infections.
- ❖ Anticholinergic nasal drops to minimize nasal mucus production. [24,25]

3) SINUSITIS

Sinusitis is an inflammation or swelling of the tissue that lines the sinuses. The sinuses are the bones between the eyes, behind the cheekbones, and the cavity of the forehead. They make mucus that keeps the inside of your nose moist. This provides protection from dust, allergens and contaminants. The conditions that can cause sinus congestion are:

- Common cold.
- Allergic rhinitis, swelling of the nasal mucosa caused by allergens.
- Small growth of nasal mucosa called nasal polyps.
- Nasal septum deviation. It is a displacement of the nasal cavity.

Types

There are types.

- **Acute sinusitis** usually begins with common cold symptoms such as runny nose, stuffy nose, and facial pain. It starts suddenly and may last for 2-4 weeks.
- **Subacute sinusitis** usually lasts 4-12 weeks.
- **Chronic sinusitis** lasts for more than 12 weeks.
- **Recurrent sinusitis** occurs several times a year. [26]

4)NASAL POLYPS

Nasal polyps are soft, painless, benign growths on the inner walls of the nasal or sinuses. They are hanging like tears and grapes. They result from chronic inflammation and are associated with asthma, recurrent infections, allergies, drug susceptibility, or certain immune disorders. Large growth or clusters of nasal polyps can block the nasal passages, cause breathing problems, loss of smell, and frequent infections. Medications can often reduce or eliminate nasal polyps, but surgery may be required to remove them.

Complications

Nasal polyps can cause complications because they interfere with normal airflow and drainage, and because of the long-term irritation and swelling (inflammation) that underlies their development. The possible complications are:

- 1) **Obstructive sleep apnea.** This is a potentially serious condition and often begins by stopping breathing during sleep.
- 2) **Asthma attack.** Chronic sinusitis can exacerbate asthma.
- 3) **Sinusitis.** Nasal polyps can make you more susceptible to the often recurrent sinus infection. [27]

MARKETED PRODUCTS[28].

DRUGS	ACTIVE PHARMACEUTICAL INGREDIENTS	MANUFACTURED BY	USED IN TREATMENT OF
Astelin	Benzalkonium chloride, Edetate disodium	Meda pharmaceuticals Inc.	Allergic rhinitis
Patanase	Benzalkonium chloride, dibasic sodium phosphate, edetate disodium	Alcon Laboratories	Allergic rhinitis , Hay fever
Mucinex	Oxymetazoline hydrochloride	Reckitt Benckiser pharmaceuticals	Hay fever , allergic rhinitis , sinusitis
Privine	Naphazoline HCL	Insight pharmaceuticals	Allergies , sinusitis
Beconase	Microcrystalline cellulose, carboxymethylcellulose sodium, benzalkonium chloride	GlaxoSmithKline	Nasal polyps
Livostin	Benzalkonium chloride, Edetate disodium, disodium phosphate	Jansen-Cilag	Management/ treatment of symptoms of seasonal and perennial rhinosinusitis
Flonase	Fluticasone propionate	GlaxoSmithKline	Nasal polyps
Nasonex	Mometasone furoate	Merck pharmaceuticals	Allergies , Nasal polyps
Nasal crom	Benzalkonium chloride, Edetate disodium	Sanofi-Aventis	Allergic symptoms , hay fever
Atrovent	Ipratropium bromide	Boehringer- Ingelheim	COPD, Chronic bronchitis , Emphysema

NASAL FORMULATIONS

Nasal drops are quantified and contain the active ingredient (drug substance) dissolved or suspended in a solution or mixture of excipients (preservatives, viscosity modifiers, emulsifiers, buffers, etc.) in non-pressurized dispensers. A material that delivers a spray containing a large amount of active ingredient. The nasal spray unit can be designed for unit administration or deliver sprays of up to hundreds of meters of the drug product containing the drug substance. Nasal sprays are applied to the nasal passages for local and / or systemic effects.

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient

The ideal nasal drug candidate should **have** the following **characteristics**:

- Appropriate **water** solubility to provide the desired dose in **dosages** of **25-150 mL**.
- Appropriate nasal absorption **characteristics**.
- No **drug** irritation **to the nose**.
- Low dose. **It is usually less than** 25 mg per dose.
- No toxic nasal metabolites.

2) Excipients used in nasal spray formulations

There are different types of excipients used in nasal formulations. Commonly used and commonly added excipients are:

a) Buffer:

Runny nose can change the pH of a dose and can affect the concentration of non-ionized drugs available for absorption. Therefore, proper formulation buffering capacity may be required to maintain pH in-situ. Examples of buffers used in nasal drops are sodium phosphate, sodium citrate, and citric acid.

b) Solubilizer:

The water solubility of a drug is a limitation of nasal administration of the drug in solution. Conventional solvents or cosolvents such as glycols, small quantities of alcohol, Transcutol (diethylene glycol monoethyl ether), medium chain glycerides and Labrasol (saturated polyglycolized C8 C10 glyceride) can be used to enhance the solubility of drugs. Other compounds can be used like, the use of surfactants or cyclodextrins such as HP- β Cyclodextrin that serve as a biocompatible solubilizer and stabilizer in combination with lipophilic absorption enhancers.

c) Preservatives:

Most nasal formulations are aqueous based so needs preservatives to prevent microbial growth. Parabens, phenylethyl alcohol, benzalkonium chloride, EDTA and benzoyl alcohol are some of the commonly used preservatives in nasal formulations.

d) Antioxidants:

A small quantity of antioxidants may be required to prevent drug oxidation. Commonly used antioxidants are sodium bisulfite, butylated hydroxytoluene, sodium metabisulfite and tocopherol. Usually, antioxidants do not affect drug absorption or cause nasal irritation.

e) Humectants:

Because of allergic and chronic diseases there can be crusts and drying of mucous membrane. Certain preservatives/antioxidants are also likely to cause nasal irritation especially when used in higher quantities. Adequate intranasal moisture is essential for preventing dehydration. Therefore, humectants can be added especially in gel-based nasal products. Humectants avoid nasal irritation and do not affect drug absorption. Common examples include glycerin, sorbitol and mannitol.

f) Surfactants :

Surfactant incorporation into nasal dosage forms can modify the permeability of nasal membranes, which may facilitate the nasal absorption of drug. It also increases stability of suspension. Common examples include Polysorbate.

g) Bioadhesive Polymers:

Compounds that interact with biological materials through interfacial forces and remain in such materials for extended periods of time are called bioadhesive polymers. If the biological membranes are mucosa, they are also called mucosal adherence. The bioadhesive strength of polymer materials depends on the type of polymer, surrounding medium (pH), swelling, and physiological factors (mucin turnover, pathology).

h) Penetration Promoters:

Chemical penetration promoters are commonly used in nasal drug delivery. [29,30]

COMMONLY UTILIZED EXCIPIENTS

Sr.No	Category	Role	Example
01	Isotonicity Adjustment	Used to adjust the tonicity of the Formulation	Sodium chloride , Dextrose
02	Ph Adjustment	Used to adjust ph same to physiological conditions and maximize drug stability	Sodium hydroxide, Hydrochloric acid , sulphuric

03	Purging	Purging used to reduce oxidation	acid Nitrogen
04	Antimicrobial Preservatives	To avoid microbial growth in the formulation	Benzalkonium chloride , ethanol , Propylene glycol , Methyl Paraben
05	Buffer component	It gives the buffer capacity to formulation at desire ph	Sodium citrate , Sodium Phosphate
06	Surfactant	Increases Suspendability and Stability of suspension	Polysorbate 80,20
07	Cation Chelating Agent	Forms chelate with ions in formulation and increases stability	Disodium EDTA
08	Suspending agents	Increases Viscosity and Suspendability of suspension	CMC , Na CMC
09	Co-solvent	Help to improve Solubility	Alcohol , PEG 400 , Propylene glycol
10	Humactant	Used to maintain humidification in the Formulation	Glycerin

CONCLUSION

The review article focused on the intranasal drug delivery system, its strengths and weaknesses, its mechanism of action, and the factors that influence nasal drug absorption. It has far fewer side effects and improved patient compliance compared to oral and parenteral drug delivery systems. Due to the many benefits of the intranasal drug delivery system. This system is of interest to many researchers. To date, IN formulations have been primarily approved and are used for topical and systemic indications not only for seasonal rhinitis and pain management, but also for emergencies such as epileptic seizures in children and adolescents. However, because BBB limits the bioavailability of drugs after systemic administration, interest in INDD is increasing for central nervous system indications such as neurodegenerative diseases and other types of CNS disorders. Increasing the number of drugs in the clinical stage and developing new nasal delivery devices will also drive the development of regulatory considerations and policies required for market approval

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